

ISic3478

I.Sicily inscription 3478

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Monte Artesino di Nicosia

Provenance

Pleiades URI: <http://pleiades.stoa.org/places/462328>

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Aci Castello, Antiquarium e museo
civico di Aci Castello

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI336137

1. [ὁ δεῖνα(?) Ἄρ]τέμωνο [ς]
2. [χρηστέ, χ]αῖρε.
- 3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645099

EDCS 70900813

PHI 336137

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 49.1299

Manganaro, G. 1999. Sikelika: studi di antichità e di epigrafia della Sicilia greca. Pisa, Roma. At 42 no.17 fig.94

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